

MULTIPLE ROLES OF TEACHER-PARENTS: BALANCING FAMILY AND CLASSROOM RESPONSIBILITIES

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Abstract. This study explored the teacher's Multiple roles of Teacher-Parents balancing the family and classroom responsibilities. Specifically, it aims to answer the experiences of teachers doing dual roles as parent and teacher at the same time and the coping mechanisms on the challenges emerging of juggling multiple roles. To achieve the objectives of the study, I made use of phenomenology. The 10 participants of this study are from Kapitán Tomas Monteverde Sr. Central Elementary School SPED Center. I used a semi-structured online interview using the coding technique in analyzing the data. The study disclosed different themes such as Difficulty in navigating dual roles and Managing emotions. Another theme is Coping with the challenges in collecting results sub-themes: Establishing boundaries and Fostering supportive classroom environment. With these themes revealed Parents who are also teachers struggle to strike a balance between their personal and professional obligations. If not handled properly, this may result in stress and burnout. Schools can assist these educators by offering flexible work schedules and work-life balance professional development. Teachers need to know how to look after themselves. This may seem a simple and easy task; however, when faced with a multitude of teaching tasks, one of the areas all teachers can miss, is taking care of themselves. Understanding and supporting teacher well-being in schools, and enabling teachers to support themselves, is essential for a sustained healthy learning environment.

KEY WORDS

1. Multiple roles 2. Juggling roles 3. Parent-Teacher

1. Introduction

Eleanor Roosevelt, author and wife of U.S. President Franklin D. Roosevelt, once said, "The giving of love is an education in itself." Mothers take on dual roles, setting timetables for learning and play. They need to control their emotions and patience, employing delayed gratification and adapting to new situations. Despite their own educational backgrounds, their concern for their children's education reflects the Filipino value of education. Mothers lack confidence in mentoring their children and rely

on teachers for education. Despite difficulties, they recognize the advantages of teaching their children, spending more time with them at home. Kokhanova et al. (2021) found that many parents were dissatisfied with distance learning due to the lack of total contact and engagement with students and teachers. Additionally, Abuhammad (2020) reported that most parents opposed remote learning due to personal, technical, logistical, and financial obstacles. Furthermore, the moms acknowledged that

they had to control their emotions and exhibit patience when teaching their children. Mothers were more anxious when the questions in the modules were challenging and they needed to conduct research to find answers. Mothers with higher educational attainment had an easier time understanding than those moms who did not. Typically, some mothers used a delayed gratification strategy with their children, preparing favorite snacks or presenting gifts after the modules were completed. When other mothers notice that their children were already sleepy, they set a time limit and gave them a break. Similarly, some mothers used tactics that they had learned in their schooling. According to Bembenutty (2021), some moms employed delayed gratification to keep their children motivated, maintained a high level of self-efficacy, and kept their cognitive and affective systems in a healthy balance. Duran and Grissmer (2020) pointed out that immediate gratification, rather than delayed gratification, might teach youngsters self-control. Furthermore, Octaberlina and Muslimi (2020) stated that providing pupils with breaks was essential for pupils to recover their energy and relax their minds. In the Philippine context, after nearly eight months of school closures, the Department of Education (DepEd) indicated that classes would resume in October 2020. However, the Department of Education mandated that blended learning and modular methodologies be used instead of face-to-face instruction. Cahapay (2021) reported that the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BELCP) of the Department of Education uses print-modular learning, television-radio, and synchronous and asynchronous teaching methods. According to Hernando-Malipot (2020), the majority of pupils favoured print-modular learning over online learning out of all the DepEd's alternative modalities. As a result of this change, students stayed at home with their mothers, who acted as their mentors. Gonzales (2020) pointed out that

the DepEd recommended parents should not act as teachers to their children but rather act as motivators and checkers to see if their children had completed their modules. Teachers, on the other hand, became module collators and assessors. Moms became teachers and, worst of all, answer-givers, because certain module questions were difficult to understand and key solutions offered were wrong. These scenarios brought further stress to a role that is already hard for mothers. According to Susilowati and Azzasyofia (2020), the added stress experienced by moms as teachers was due to their inability to supervise their children's education. The absence of learning tools, such as an internet connection and the digital literacy abilities of mothers, is cited by Putra et al. (2020) as a source of difficulty in home-based schooling. The researchers hypothesized that parental characteristics such as socio-economic status and educational attainment can contribute to teaching efficacy. Philippine mothers are now known for combining traditional and modern parenting techniques. This means that their commitment and perseverance are not confined to domestic responsibilities. They also strive for well-being in all parts of their lives, especially for their children (Terol, 2016). Rojas (2017) went on to say that Philippine women are good nurturers of their children. According to Hierarchy Structure (2018), moms are the first teachers of children in a Philippine home. Given these traits of Philippine women, it would be fascinating to see how they adapted to their new responsibilities of teaching their children as a result of the pandemic. Davao City is a very progressive city in which the roles of teachers are complicated. The need to wake up early is a routine of being a mother at the same time, speeding up the duties of being a parent that really involves efficient functions to both. In most schools in Davao City Division is having these roles. That needs also to be heard and address their sentiments.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this research study is to identify teachers' perceptions of being a mother at the same a teacher. This study also aims to identify their coping mechanisms to address the said challenges. This is to know the different challenges that teachers experience in dealing with being a mother at the same a teacher.

1.2. Research Questions—The study aims to investigate teachers perceived as both a teacher and a mother, It also looked into their first-hand experiences of being mothers and teachers to their children. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences of teachers doing dual roles as a mother and as a teacher?
- (2) How do they cope with the challenges of juggling multiple roles?
- (3) What educational insights are drawn from the study?

The highlights of the study were significant to the following: Teachers are given insight into what are the experiences and challenges of teachers that other teachers have when it comes to dealing with school head's leadership. This would help them prepare as they would have an idea of how to solve problems that may occur while utilizing the approach. Policy/program implementors could use the results of this study to create policies and programs for teachers in order for them to help the teachers in the better implementation of teaching and learning. Lastly, this research would help other researchers if they wish to conduct a similar or comparative study.

1.3. Definition of Terms—Multiple Roles. provide students with personalized teaching, cater to different learning styles, and evaluate the progress of their students on a regular basis. As well as monitoring academic progress, teachers nurture a positive mental attitude and positive mental health through continuous mentoring and personal pastoral care. Teacher-Parent. The authority to make decisions concerning and affecting the care, welfare, and proper development of the child is known as 'parental responsibility'. Balance Family. term for gender selection done for the purpose of achieving a more balanced representation of both genders in a family. Classroom Responsibilities. duties related to a teacher's specific assignment or pupil duties that are co-involved in the efficient operations of the school and enhancement of pupil education.

1.4. Theoretical Lens—This research is highly anchored on two propositions. First, the concept of the dual roles of the mother as a teacher, and second, family stress. According to Claesson and Brice (2019), the dual roles of the mother and teacher are complementary. Expectations for both roles, however, were vague and, in some cases, overly high. Nonetheless, as teachers, mothers gained understanding and learned coping and benefiting skills for their dual function. In the context of the COVID 19 pandemic, de Jong et al. (2021) noted that evidently the homeschooling of children had put extra demands on mothers who, according to Darmody et al. (2020) and Moore et al. (2020), assumed more responsibilities in the household. On the other hand, family stress involves stressors that affect the family such as physical and mental health concerns, economic, intensified child-parent relationships, and home schooling (Wu Xu, 2020). Family stressors can also be characterized into three layers of family mean-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

ings: (1) situational meanings, (2) family identity, and (3) family worldview (Patterson Garwick, 2014). The occurrence of COVID-19 can be considered a situation meaning. Cassinat et al. (2021) found that the pandemic increased strain and commotion within the many families, and these changes had ramifications for numerous family connections, consistent with a

family stress perspective. These two concepts were appropriate in the current study because they looked into the new roles of mothers with school-aged children and, at the same time, determined the stresses the COVID-19 pandemic had brought to the mother and child relationship.

The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. As seen in the figure, there are three interconnected variables. The Experiences of teachers to a servant type of leadership, a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers and teachers to provide the necessary skills, knowledge, and focus on engaging in meaningful inquiry about their professional practice would enhance this practice and effect positive changes concerning the educative goals

of the learning community. There is a real concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; however, the center of the two circles determines that there is a connection between exploring the experiences of teachers when it comes to the servant leadership approach is important to the improvement of teaching and learning process for the curriculum.

1.5. *Framework Analysis*—According to Braun and Clark (2006), methods of qualitative data analysis fall in two groups. The first group consists of methods driven by an epistemological or theoretical position, which have limited variability in how they are applied within their frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) and methods that are situated within a broad theoretical framework and can there-

fore be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks, such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA) narrative analysis (NA). The second group includes methods independent of theory and epistemology, which can be applied across a range of different theoretical and epistemological approaches and are therefore very flexible. One such method is thematic analysis, which through the theoretical freedom “provides flexible and useful research

tool, which can potentially provide a rich and detailed, yet complex account of data (Braun and Clark, 2006). I observed several steps in conducting thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my own resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I use several nights to listen to the interviews to deepen my understanding of the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing to conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated themselves to lay out and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step is data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note-taking and summary while

listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues, or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used a number of different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. I used forms of thematic grids and charts, the framework technique as developed by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al, 2003). This technique was useful to me in the process of coding, sorting, and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedures included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross-referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) which consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data.

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sisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data.

- (1) Phase 1. I familiarized myself with the data by reading the whole data set and noting down initial ideas;
- (2) Phase 2. I generated initial codes, with code being the most basic segments of the raw data that can identify a feature of the data that appears interesting;
- (3) Phase 3. I searched for themes by sorting different codes into potential themes and collated all data extracts within identified themes;
- (4) Phase 4. I reviewed the themes and refined them further (at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set) and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub themes;
- (5) Phase 5. I defined and named themes, making sure they give the reader immediate sense of what the theme is all about.
- (6) I wrote the report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes), used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments in relation to the research question.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

2. Method

This chapter will introduce the methods that will be used in conducting the study and the gathering of data. This also includes the research design, philosophical assumptions, research participants and sampling, data collection, research instrument, the trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) is optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry which asks the questions, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "The goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of the school heads in the new normal as they try to compare its implementation then and now. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. A good research – undertaking with the selection of the topic, problem or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Decent study-task jumps with the range of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (2007) traced the 'paradigm' back to its Greek (*paradeigma*) and Latin origins (*paradigm*) meaning pattern, model, or example. A paradigm is the patterning of the thinking of a person; it is a principal example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm is an act of submitting to a view (Stanage 2007). This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000) who define a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action", dealing with first principles, 'ultimates' or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality is constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realist exists, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, realities on the implementation of the curriculum in the past and the present are discussed by the participants and tries to look into their ways in coping with the implementation in the new normal. In this study, I relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidences of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher

upheld the authenticity of the responses and precludes from making personal bias as the study progress. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study in order to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985) as cited by Creswell (2013) state that on epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an "insider." Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). I will identify phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief". The intention of this study is to gather information from the participants as to how they implemented the program following the guidelines set by DepEd and the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF). I assured to establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that will shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly

2.2. *Qualitative Assumption of the Study*—The methodology is different from the method. The methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the experiences of the teachers were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI) as well as their coping strategies were extracted from the participants. The researcher's inquisitiveness on the experiences of the School Heads became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena". By using phenomenol-

ogy, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the teachers having dual roles in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences will be presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first is that experience is a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn on the experiences and the coping strategies of the teachers in implementing the program in the new normal. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2013) avers that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes own interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and the value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. I therefore preserve the merit of the participant's answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participant's personal interpretation. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice and uses qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person in the elucidation of the experiences of the teachers as they adopt to the new mode of learning implementation amidst the pandemic.

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much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which concerns with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995),

the researcher hoped that the subjective experiences and perspectives of the participants would provide highlights as to how the program was implemented before COVID-19 and the present execution of the program.

2.3. Research Design—This study utilized a qualitative phenomenological research design. The phenomenological design describes the interpretations of the participants from their experiences. The participants were required to respond to the questions provided to them via Google Forms. After, they were requested to participate in a Focus Group Discussion virtually and face to face, depending on the situation. At the end of this study, themes and common patterns were extracted from their responses (JamonCaban, 2019). They decided to use a qualitative phenomenological research design because they would dwell on the individual experiences of the teachers under the new normal in Philippine public education. There were 10 school heads as participants of the study who had firsthand experiences in the new normal in Philippine public education. The data gathered were recorded, transcribed, and validated to extract the first-hand experiences on the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the new normal in Philippine public education from the secondary teachers' lived experiences. The Colaizzi method of data analysis in a phenomenological research design was used. This is purely academic. The participants

signed the informed consent, and there is no risk in this study. They can anytime withdraw as a participant of the study. Ethical considerations and safety health protocols were followed. A phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon (Creswell, 2013). Typically, interviews are conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994): What have you experienced in terms of the phenomenon? What contexts or situations have typically influenced your experiences of the phenomenon (Creswell, 2013)? Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, may also be used. The data is then read and reread and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this process, the researcher may construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon.

2.4. Ethical Considerations—Creswell (2007) emphasized that qualitative researchers face many ethical issues that surface during data collection in the field and analysis and dissemination of qualitative reports. In this study, the researcher will deal with former teachers in public schools. To ensure an authentic response from the participants, the researcher

will be responsible for exercising extra caution and maintaining the confidentiality of the study. The rights of the participants will be extremely considered. Besides, they will not be forced to be part of the study when they will refuse. In protecting the identity of the participants, Glesne and Peshkins (1992) suggested that providing and assigning numbers

or aliases can protect the anonymity of the participants. In this study, I used codes to protect the identity of the participants. Added to this, as the researcher, I explained the purpose and significance of the study. The participants will be given the chance to question the researcher about the nature of the study. This certifies that the information is clear to the participants. Moreover, the data gathering and the participation of the participants are guided by the Informed Consent Form, which is signed by the chosen participants. Lastly, the results and findings will be presented back to the participants for verification. The transcriptions of the recorded interview will be kept private. Further, each of the participants will be advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview is carried out. This would provide the participants with the opportunity to amend or remove any information which they feel might identify them. The researcher will reserve the right to employ the use of pseudonyms, and changing names and or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher will ensure that he or she possesses the needed qualification to conduct the study. The researcher should be completing the academic requirements, passed the comprehensive examination before thesis writing which will be the last requirement to obtain the master's degree, and that the researcher should be qualified to conduct the study physically, men-

tally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher will strive that the study can be completed successfully at the specified time and that he or she is equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee will be of help in the enhancement of the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations for the improvement of the study. Also, the researcher would ensure that he or she has enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoping to be completed at the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher will be showing respect to the local tradition, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study will not be involved in any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, and specifically, in the recruitment of the participants, or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher would necessarily express great pleasure for the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher will respect other works by properly citing the author and rewrite what someone else has said his or her way. The researcher would also always use quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher would assure that honesty is present in working the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data and or results are included, or purposefully putting forward conclusions that are not accurate

2.5. *Research Participants*—In the selection of the research participants, purposive sampling will be applied. Purposive sampling is a sampling technique in which the researcher relies on his or her own judgment when choos-

ing members of the population to participate in the study. It is a non-probability sampling method, and it occurs when elements selected for the sample are chosen by the judgment of the researcher. Researchers often believe that

they can obtain a representative sample by using sound judgment, which will result in saving time and money (Black, 2010). In this study, suitable samples include ten (10) teachers with children who were public school teachers either male or female teacher in Kapitan Tomas Monteverde Sr. Central Elementary School SPED

2.6. Research Instrument—In this study, I made use of an Interview Guide Question Tool with sub-questions for the in-depth online interview. The tool was used as my guide while interviewing with the selected teachers who will be my participants in the recorded in-depth online interview. That aimed to answer the research questions and to collect additional inputs that can be of use in my study. To address the validity issues of this design, specifically on the method, I would ask for help from the experts. My interview guide question tool that were checked and validated by the experts. The sampling that was used for the selection of my participants was based on the suggestions of the expert panels. In the identification of these research informants, there will be ten (10) public school teachers either male or female teachers from Kapitan Tomas Monteverde Sr. Central Elementary School SPED Center,

2.7. Data Collection—According to Creswell (2013), an important step in the process is to find people or places to study and to gain access to and establish rapport with participants so that they will provide good data. A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data, such as

Center, Davao Central District, Davao City Division. There will be ten (10) informants who will be part of the in-depth interview. Moreover, to protect the identity of the participants, coding will be used. IDI-FT1 to IDI-FT10 will be used for the informants of the in-depth interview.

Davao Central District, Davao City Division. Purposive sampling will be used especially exemplified through the key informant technique wherein one or a few individuals solicited to act as guides to a culture (Tongco, 2007). I used a referral system so that I could be able to access teachers who would help qualify my criteria. This system is also called snowball sampling. Snowball sampling is a non-probability-based sampling technique that was used to gain access to such populations. The participants will be purposely chosen so that the information needed could expedite the study. However, the application of snowball sampling will later be appropriated to gather the exact data needed to answer the research questions. Moreover, the identity of my participants will be strictly valued and respected under the "ethics of research." Hence, the researcher's interaction with them will be collegial and morally upright.

an interview or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues of data collection, called "field issues," which may be a problem, such as having inadequate data, needing to prematurely leave the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she will store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In gathering data, strict compliance to IATF protocols were observed. The researcher secured a letter of permission to the participants and send it via email. Upon approval, the researcher used

the forms of data collection as prescribed in the qualitative design. In this study, recording an in-depth interview and focus group discussion have been used. The researcher needs to get the subjective interaction between the participants of the study. The researcher heavily relied on naturalistic methods (interviewing and audio-recording) and the interpretive paradigm were used. Interpretive approaches rely heavily on naturalistic methods like interviewing and observation and analysis of existing texts. These methods ensure an adequate dialog between the researchers and those with whom they interact to collaboratively construct a meaningful reality. Yin as cited by Aquilam (2014) suggested numerous forms of data collection, as follows: documents, archival records, interviews, direct observation, participant observation, and physical artifacts. To have legitimate and trustworthy data on the experiences of teachers with regards to the new normal way of teaching and learning, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview and focus group discussion. The interview aimed to gather information on the feelings and experiences of teachers. The participants have been encouraged to express their answers in their most comfortable manner. The interview with the participants has been transcribed

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with a full description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher’s personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then finds statements about how individuals were experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping

word for word. Lastly, the researcher analyzed the data collected using discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Creswell (2007) suggested that succeeding in the conduct of the study, the data must be stored so that they can easily be found and protected from damage and loss. Furthermore, Interviews has also strengths and weaknesses. One of the strengths of an interview is that the interviews provide useful information when participants cannot be directly observed. The interviewer has better control over the types of information that they receive. They can also pick their questions. If worded effectively, questions would encourage unbiased and truthful answers. However, one of the weaknesses is that the interviewee may provide biased information or be unreliable if only one interviewer is interpreting the information. The best research requires many different points of view. The answers may be deceptive because the interviewee tries to respond in a way that would please the interviewer. Then, equipment may be costly and require a high level of technical competence to be used and it can be time-consuming, and inexperienced interviewers may not be able to keep the questions properly focused (Quad, 2016).

statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information, called “meaning units” or themes. She wrote a description of “what” the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, he wrote a description of “how” the experience happened. This was called “structural description,” and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the “essence” of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study.

2.9. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Trustworthiness is all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability. In qualitative study, trustworthiness is very important because the result and finding of the research study would depend on the process of how it is being conducted by the researcher. Trustworthiness of a research study is important to evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details are required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher's study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. The concepts of validity and reliability are relatively foreign to the field of qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness. Trustworthiness consists of the following components: credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility contributes to a belief in the trustworthiness of data by observing the attributes of prolonged engagement. To address the issue of credibility, interviewed as many research participants as possible or up to the point of saturation. Transferability is concerned with the extent to which the findings of one study can be applied to other situations. In positivist work, the concern often lies in demonstrating

that the results of the work at hand can be applied to a wider population since the findings of a qualitative project are specific to a small number of particular environments and individuals. It is impossible to demonstrate that the findings and conclusions apply to other situations and populations. Therefore, to ensure transferability, I acknowledged that it is my responsibility as a researcher to ensure that sufficient contextual transformation about the fieldwork sites is provided to enable the reader to make such a transfer. Confirmability associates objectivity in science with the use of instruments that are not dependent on human skill and perception. It is, however, difficult to ensure real objectivity since, as even tests and questionnaires are designed by humans, the intrusion of the researcher's biases is inevitable. Here, steps must be taken to help ensure as far as possible that the work's findings are the result of the experiences and ideas of the participants, rather than the characteristics and preferences of the researcher. Dependability involves participant's evaluation of the findings, interpretation and recommendations of the study such that all are supported by the data as received from participants of the study. Confirmability: The degree to which the findings of the research study could be confirmed by other researchers.

3. Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter were the results generated from the analysis of the data from the interview. It presented themes that emerge from the analysis. Along with the themes were comprehensive discussions that answer the objectives of the study. Before I begin my discussion, I established the symbols I used as I present the quotations based on the responses of the participants of the study. In reference to the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, I used pseudonyms to refer to the participants of the research.

3.1. *Experiences of Teachers Doing Dual Roles as a Mother and as a Teacher*—The first objective of the study is to explore the teacher

experience in doing the dual role. From the interview conducted, several themes have been found. Firstly, the teachers experience difficulty in navigating the dual role.

3.1.1. *Difficulty in Navigating Dual Roles.*—

The first theme under the experiences of teachers in doing dual roles is the difficulty in navigating dual roles. Teachers who are also mothers of their students have to navigate the dual roles of teacher and parent. This means balancing their responsibilities as a teacher and their responsibilities as a mother, often with the same group of students. Teacher reports of children's competence and problem behaviors are an important source of information on psychopathology. The school context is also an agent of developmental change. This study examines teacher-child relationships and deflections in child adjustment over the school-entry to grade 2 period in 436 children. The Student-Teacher Relationship Scale (STRS) was related to two indices of deflections in predicted child adjustment: (a) residual scores obtained from regressing teacher reports from grade 1 on kindergarten teacher reports, and (b) false positive predictions of retention or referral for special education in the K-I period. Children with whom kindergarten teachers reported a positive relationship were rated in spring of grade I as better adjusted than was predicted on the basis of identical ratings from the fall of the kindergarten year; the converse was also true. False-positive retention/referral predictions had more positive relationships with kindergarten teachers than did true positives. A second set of analyses examined second grade teacher ratings of child adjustment and child-teacher relationships in two groups of children with different child-teacher relationship histories in kindergarten. Children with warm, close, communicative relationships with kindergarten teachers were better adjusted and had more positive child-teacher relationships in second grade than those with angry, dependent child-teacher relationships in kindergarten. Results supported the view that children's relationships with teachers are an important component of adaptation in school and that they can play a role in deflecting the course of development in the school context. Teachers play an important role in the trajectory of students throughout the formal schooling experience (Baker, Grant, Morlock, 2008). Although most research regarding teacher-student relationships investigates the elementary years of schooling, teachers have the unique opportunity to support student's academic and social development at all levels of schooling (Baker et al., 2008; Bronfenbrenner, 1979; Bronfenbrenner Morris, 1998; McCormick, Cappella, O'Connor, McClowry, in press). Aligned with attachment theory (Ainsworth, 2012), positive teacher-student relationships enable students to feel safe and secure in their learning environments and provide scaffolding for important social and academic skills (Baker et al., 2008;). Teachers who support students in the learning environment can positively impact their social and academic outcomes, which is important for the long-term trajectory of school and eventually employment (Baker et al., 2008; O'Connor et al., 2011; Silver et al., 2005). When teachers form positive bonds with students, classrooms become supportive spaces in which students can engage in academically and socially productive ways (Hamre Pianta, 2001). Positive teacher-student relationships are classified as having the presence of closeness, warmth, and positivity (Hamre Pianta, 2001). Students who have positive relationships with their teachers use them as a secure base from which they can explore the classroom and school setting both academically and socially, to take on academic challenges and work on social-emotional development (Hamre Pianta, 2001). This includes relationships with peers, and developing self-esteem and self-concept (Hamre Pianta, 2001). Through this secure relationship, students learn about socially appropriate behaviors as well as academic expectations and how to achieve these expectations (Hamre Pianta, 2001). Students in low-income schools can especially benefit from positive relationships with teachers (Murray Malmgren, 2005). Students

in high-poverty urban schools may benefit from positive teacher-student relationships even more than students in high-income schools, because of the risks associated with poverty (Murray Malmgren, 2005). Risk outcomes associated with poverty include high rates of high school dropout, lower rates of college applications, low self-efficacy, and low self-confidence (Murray Malmgren, 2005). There are several factors that can protect against the negative outcomes often associated with low-income schooling, one of which is a positive and supportive relationship with an adult, most often a teacher (Murray Malmgren, 2005). Low-income students who have strong teacher-student relationships have higher academic achievement and have more positive social-emotional adjustment than their peers who do not have a positive relationship with a teacher (Murray Malmgren, 2005). There is substantial research on the importance of teacher-student relationships in the early elementary years (Pianta, 1992; Hamre Pianta 2001). However, little is known about the effects of teacher-student relationships on high school students. Studies show that early teacher-student relationships affect early academic and social outcomes as well as future academic outcomes (Pianta 1992; Hamre Pianta 2001), but few researchers have looked at the effects of teacher-student relationships in later years of schooling. Researchers who have investigated teacher-student relationships for older students have found that positive teacher-student relationships are associated with positive academic and social outcomes for high school students (KewallRamani, 2009). Education has improved greatly in recent years. Likewise, parents are gradually placing more emphasis on the importance of their children's education, especially on the quality of teaching. Under the impact of the low birth rate, many parents are concerned about education. At the same time, concerns about teacher competence are worth discussing. Regardless of the high investment in education, access to good software–hardware in schools, and higher quality students, these components are meaningless without a “good teacher. Teachers play an important role in the effectiveness of education. In recent years, many serious crimes have caused the society to worry about the shortage of manpower and insufficient expertise or skills on campus. Since school work is done by general teachers, counseling work cannot be done effectively. Prior to the outbreak of the incidents, education staffs are unaware of the importance of counseling and ignore the hidden signs of the crisis on campus, for example, bullying, gender equity, and high-risk students. Student-related problems can be ignored and may not be seen as a problem for the future. In addition, many people in the society do not have a proper understanding of school work, have false expectations of teachers' work, and falsely attribute student responsibility to teachers, believing that teachers can and should do everything. Such a strong role pressure causes deep frustration and helplessness among teachers, who gradually lose their passion for the work. The reasons behind this are the teachers playing complicated and multiple roles. They are responsible for guiding students with deviant behaviors, consulting with teachers or parents, and helping with work-related issues in schools. This leads to excessive pressure and burnout among teachers and even makes them consider changing jobs. Teachers start to procrastinate and get tired. They not only have to think about problems, but also control their emotions. They also need to improve themselves and find a way to take care of themselves after work. Modern national education reform is about promoting the performance and quality of national education. National education reform is a recent trend, but its effectiveness depends on the front-line executors, that is, the cooperation of teachers. Without a “good” teacher, the large investment in education, the good software–hardware of schools, and the high quality

of students would be “in vain.” It is as in the saying “excellent teachers build a nation,” which applies to the past and also to the present and to education at the national level and abroad. Education, as a fundamental task that is crucial for generations, influences the future development and competitiveness of a nation. Teachers in the new age should present Pädagogische Liebe (pedagogical love), professional competence, and capacity for the future. They should also stick to student-centeredness in classrooms, diligently and orderly develop the imperceptible and mind-changing educational function, and bear the burden of educational effectiveness. It can be seen that teachers’ classroom practices emphasize the promotion of educational performance and quality. Obviously, the effectiveness of teachers’ role practices is the key to the success of education reform; the importance of teachers’ role practices in educational effectiveness is obvious. From the perspective of school education, teacher’s performance can directly affect the effectiveness of the school. In other words, teacher’s performance directly affects the achievement of schools’ educational goals

3.1.2. Managing Emotions—The second theme under the experiences of teachers in doing the dual role is managing emotions in every situation. Teachers who are also mothers of their students might experience heightened emotions when it comes to their child’s academic or social experiences in the classroom. They might feel a greater sense of pride or disappointment when it comes to their child’s performance, which can impact their ability to be objective in their teaching approach. Teachers experience a variety of discrete emotions of varying intensity while teaching and interacting with students (Sutton and Wheatley, 2003; Meyer and Turner, 2007; Schutz et al., 2007; Sutton, 2007; Spilt et al., 2011; Frenzel, 2014; Burić et al., 2018). These emotions are related to teachers’

and is indirectly related to the students’ attitudes and expectations for learning performance. The profession of teaching requires a high level of expertise, so educators should be treated as professionals and teachers’ specialization should be confirmed to promote the teachers’ professional development. The increased level of knowledge in recent years has made parents more concerned about their children’s learning equity. This may lead to differences between parents and teachers regarding the essence of teaching, learning, and evaluation, but the conflict is often heard. In this case, curriculum, instruction, and performance contents are often affected by the parents, which prevents teachers from teaching with professional knowledge—competence and developing professional autonomy. In addition, due to social change, the issues, such as the complexity of family structure and the increasing student problems, are becoming more complicated. Accordingly, schools sometimes have to take over the function of the family. Teachers are the front-line people and experience bridging families and schools most of the time.

instructional practices and their relationships with students, as well as to students’ learning outcomes (Sutton and Wheatley, 2003; Weiner,). Moreover, teachers’ emotions contribute to their professional well-being since they may shape burnout levels and job satisfaction, or influence the decision to leave the teaching profession (Macdonald, 1999; Meyer and Turner, 2007; Schutz et al., 2007; Chang, 2009, 2013; Frenzel et al., 2009). Finally, teachers’ emotions seem to be closely related to teacher motivational aspects such as work engagement (Halbesleben, 2010). Teacher self-efficacy (TSE), that is, a teacher’s level of confidence in executing a variety of profession-related activities such as influencing student learning and managing the learning environment (Tschannen-Moran and Hoy,

2001), is one of the most salient motivational characteristics that affect classroom processes and student academic adjustment (Burić and Kim, 2020). In addition, TSE has been extensively researched in relation to different aspects of teachers' well-being such as burnout, stress and coping, job satisfaction, and professional commitment (Caprara et al., 2006)). Regardless the existing research on the role of teachers' emotions and TSE in explaining their instructional practices, students' outcomes, and diverse well-being indicators, the nature of the relationship between teachers' emotions and TSE has been rarely studied. Several studies showed that higher levels of TSE are positively related to teachers' positive emotions (e.g., joy, pride) and negatively to teachers' negative emotions (e.g., anger, anxiety; Borrachero et al., 2013; Frenzel et al., 2016; Pitkäniemi, 2017; Burić et al., 2018; Burić and Frenzel, 2019). In addition, TSE was found to predict preservice teachers' practicum performance positively via positive emotions (e.g., love and joy) and negatively via negative emotions (e.g., fear, sadness, and anger; Chen, 2019a). However, since these studies were based on cross-sectional design, the nature and the directionality of the relationship between teachers' emotions and TSE have remained unknown. Understanding whether TSE causes teachers' emotions or teachers' emotions influence TSE may be the first step in effective policy development and intervention implementation that could enhance teachers' emotional well-being and/or motivation. Therefore, the aim of the present research was to examine the directionality of the association between TSE and a set of discrete emotions (i.e., joy, pride, love, anger, exhaustion, and hopelessness) that teachers experience while teaching and interacting with students. In recent years, emotions have been recognized as integral parts of teachers' professional lives. Teachers' emotions are related to students and their learning, teachers themselves and teaching, as well as to contextual factors (e.g., collegial relationships, principal support, parent's expectations, educational policies; Wu and Chen, 2018). Even though teachers' emotions may arise from factors at school (e.g., colleagues and administration), the community (e.g., parents) and from a societal level (e.g., culture and politics), emotions that stem from teaching and interacting with students are the most frequent and intense ones (Chen, 2019b). Teachers rather frequently experience a wide variety of discrete emotions while teaching and interacting with students such as joy, satisfaction, pride, love, anger, exhaustion, hopelessness, anxiety, shame, or boredom (Sutton and Wheatley, 2003; Frenzel et al., 2016; Burić et al., 2018; Chen, 2019b). Such emotions are evoked by a variety of classroom situations and events. For instance, students' violation of classroom rules or disrespectful behavior toward other students may trigger anger in teachers (Burić and Frenzel, 2019). In contrast, when students strive and succeed academically, teachers may experience joy or pride (Burić et al., 2018). These two examples clearly illustrate that teaching activities and interactions with students are strong sources of teachers' emotions. Therefore, understanding the causes and triggers of teachers' emotions, but also their consequences, is of great importance for optimal teachers' functioning in the classrooms. The reciprocal model on causes and effects of teacher emotions (Frenzel, 2014) offers a useful theoretical framework for investigating the antecedents and effects of teachers' emotions. According to this model, teachers hold multiple classroom goals (i.e., to develop students' subject-specific and socio-emotional competencies, to motivate students, and to establish well-functioning relationships with students) whose attainment is evaluated through teachers' perceptions of students' behaviors in the classroom. Specifically, based on observation of students' behaviors, teachers appraise whether they accomplished their goals, whether students' behavior helped

Fig. 3. Educational Insights Drawn from the Study

them in reaching their goals, and whether they felt competent and capable of achieving their goals. In addition, teachers evaluate who is responsible for attaining (or not attaining) classroom goals as well as how important these goals are. Depending on the content of these cognitive appraisals, different teachers' emotions may emerge. For instance, for teachers whose goal is to motivate students to learn a certain material by implementing a new teaching method, observation of their students as uninterested and uncooperative could lead to the appraisal of poor coping potential due to insufficient teaching ex-

perience and evoke feelings of hopelessness. In contrast, teachers who observe that students make progress and are highly engaged in learning when the material is presented through a new teaching method, may evaluate that their goal is accomplished and consequently experience enjoyment. Finally, according to the model, emotions that result from such cognitive appraisals shape different aspects of teachers' instructional behavior, that is, cognitive and motivational stimulation, classroom management, and social support (Frenzel, 2014).

Even though the reciprocal model of causes and effects of teacher emotions does not explicitly emphasize the role of TSE in shaping cognitive appraisals and consequently teachers' emotions, it can be assumed that teachers with higher levels of self-efficacy would have more positive evaluation of their coping potential since they may evaluate themselves as more capable of attaining and optimizing their class-

room goals. Such greater coping potential may contribute to the experience of positive teachers' emotions such as joy or pride. Conversely, teachers with low levels of self-efficacy may appraise their potential to cope with obstacles while attaining and optimizing their classroom goals as poorer, which may lead to the experience of negative emotions such as anger or anxiety.

3.2. *Coping Mechanism with the Challenges of Juggling Multiple Roles*—Another object of this study is to explore the different coping mechanisms that teachers employ to address the challenges of the teachers in juggling mul-

iple roles. From the interviews, the teachers shared that the coping mechanism that teachers employ to address their challenges and dual roles is to establish boundaries and foster a supportive classroom environment.

3.2.1. *Establish boundaries*—

One of the coping mechanisms that teachers employ to address the challenges of doing dual roles is to establish boundaries. Teachers who are also mothers of their students can benefit from setting clear boundaries between their personal and professional lives. This might mean setting specific times for grading and lesson planning and then prioritizing time with their family outside of school hours. Maintaining personal, professional and protective boundaries is a crucial consideration for those working in our schools. Sarah Morgan offers guidance for teachers and education professionals. Professional boundaries are an essential part of our work as teachers. How we present ourselves, our interaction with others and our general conduct are highly significant when working directly with the pupils in our classroom. Our personal presentation and professional conduct reduces the risk of allegations and keeps pupils safe from harm. The report, *Allegations of Abuse Against Teachers and Non-Teaching Staff* (DfE, 2011) presented findings suggesting that the number of allegations made against teachers between April 2009 and March 2010 was 2,827, and that almost a fifth of teachers were suspended while an allegation was investigated. Data is patchy and there is no central mechanism for recording allegations and the outcomes. Safeguarding pupils, and protecting yourself from the risk of allegation, is a key professional priority. Personal and professional boundary-setting should seamlessly flow through all interaction and intervention within the school. Boundaries shape our relationships with children, families, care-givers and professional colleagues. We know that pupils can often arrive in our classrooms from a range of backgrounds. They may have experienced differing and complex home lives, varying styles of parenting, and often differing, and sometimes-confused social expectations, norms and inconsistent boundary-setting. This inevitably brings professional challenges. Boundary “holding” does not mean that your relationships should be cold and detached. You can and should offer authentic warmth to support and build professional relationships with pupils, and their families, without placing them or yourself at risk. In this article, we have drawn together some key areas of boundary-setting that teachers should be sensitive to. The Education Act 2002 imposes clear duties to provide acceptable levels of care and to protect children and young people from all reasonably foreseeable risk of harm or injury. Duty of Care refers to the responsibility of those staff members, employed within a position of trust, to provide pupils with adequate levels of protection against harm and to safeguard their welfare at all times. What constitutes “reasonable and acceptable care” in any given case will be determined objectively by the court and will depend upon the circumstances of each case. The standard of care expected from schools is understandably very high. The teacher-pupil relationship is not equal. Teachers and all education professionals are in a unique position of trust, care, responsibility, authority and influence with their pupils. This means that there is always an inherent power imbalance within the teacher-pupil dynamic. With this in mind, you may wish to explore the following suggestions openly and reflectively within your school. The examples are given as a guide, and are by no means exhaustive. You may wish to add to the listings provided, as you collectively explore and reflect upon boundaries within your school. You can and should develop good strong trusting relationships with the pupils that you teach, but you are not “friends” with them. On this basis always be thoughtful about the language that you might be using. Sensitive thought and challenge should be explored in relation to inappropriate language or terms. Examples to avoid include: Work and home or the personal and the professional should be held separately. Remaining “in role” at all times minimizes the likelihood of false, or unfounded allegations and ensures

that professional codes of conduct are adhered to. Examples to avoid: Inviting, allowing, or encouraging pupils to attend your home. Allowing pupils access to a staff member's personal internet locations and personal devices (e.g. social networking sites). Attending pupils' homes or their social gatherings. Being alone with a pupil outside of a staff member's responsibilities unless agreed upon by a senior leader. Entering changing rooms or toilets occupied by pupils when supervision is not required or appropriate or using toilet facilities allocated to pupils. Undressing using facilities set aside for pupils, or in their presence. Transporting a pupil unaccompanied without prior permission. One-to-one tutoring, mentoring, or coaching of pupils without the prior agreement of the head teacher. Giving personal gifts or special favors. Singling the same pupils out for special duties or responsibilities. Offering overnight, weekend, or holiday care as a respite to parents without the prior knowledge of the head teacher. Be careful not to collude with pupils. Be aware that children and young people can draw adults into conversations and situations. We should always remain within the boundaries of our professional role. Challenge anti-discriminatory language/jokes. We are role models to the pupils we work with, and it is important that we promote and respect differences. We also have a responsibility to challenge negative ideas, assumptions, behavior,

and language whenever it occurs. This is how children will learn new ways of thinking about themselves and others. Avoid discussing information regarding other pupils or members of staff. Be aware of being overheard while on the telephone or on your mobile phone. Avoid giving pupils gifts and lending or borrowing items. There are issues of power, control, and equality involved in these areas. Pupils should be discouraged from offering gifts to staff. Maintain high levels of appearance and personal self-care. We are professionals at work and as such represent the school. You are modeling self-respect, core values, expectations, and consistent approaches. Our moods and feelings affect our thinking and most importantly our communication. This is also true of our non-verbal communication: body language, eye contact, and facial expressions. This can have a huge impact on our interactions with pupils and colleagues alike. We are all human and we may have things going on in our lives at work or at home that will affect our mood, attitude, judgment, emotional presentation, and possibly our demeanor. As professionals, we must learn to separate these issues when we are working directly with pupils. Our personal issues are not problems for pupils to be a party to, and they should be protected from unhelpful exposure to our personal or professional challenges or emotional difficulties.

3.2.2. *Foster a Supportive Classroom Environment*—Another coping mechanism that teachers employ to cope with the challenges in doing dual roles is fostering a supportive classroom environment. Teachers who are also mothers of their students can benefit from fostering a supportive classroom environment where all students feel valued and respected. This can help to minimize any potential conflicts or biases that might arise due to their dual roles. It is important to foster a learning environment

in which students feel safe, relaxed, and willing to take risks, especially for learners who may have had negative experiences in traditional classroom environments. Students often describe supportive learning environments as expanding their sense of family and enhancing their self-esteem, which, when combined with increased literacy skills, help students take more chances in pursuing their goals. Build a strong classroom community. The adult education classroom can play an important role in

helping students build stronger and larger networks. Classrooms provide students and staff with friendship, skills, and contacts beyond their immediate communities. Intentionally building networks in the classroom can create meaningful, supportive relationships among students and teachers. Use pair work, as well as small-group and whole-class activities, beginning the first day of class to help students get acquainted, and provide ongoing opportunities for students to form connections with students they don't interact with as frequently in the classroom. Provide students with opportunities to share about their backgrounds and cultures. Seek to connect students with the greater community, through field trips, current events discussions, bringing guest speakers, etc. See our website for information on monthly workshops and field trips that teach about community involvement and service while improving language skills. Build self-esteem and self-efficacy. Students' determination and belief that they can achieve their goals are important factors in their persistence in ongoing learning. Adult learners may have negative feelings about themselves due to failure experienced in their lives, due to dropping out of school, losing a job, or not being able to read or write well enough to complete a job application or read to their children. Ensure that students experience success at their first meeting so the first experience is a positive one. It may be appropriate to start with material that is slightly below the student's level. Be patient! Patience is an extremely important characteristic for any teacher or tutor of adults. Adults can often take a longer time in the learning process because of various learning barriers, but this does not mean they aren't motivated to learn. Accept your student as he/she is and respect his/her values even if they differ from yours. Believe in your student and he/she will begin to believe in him/herself. Memorize the names of all your students within the first week of instruction. Use students' names frequently. If your

students are English learners, learn a few key phrases in their native languages to model that it is acceptable to struggle with pronunciation and language learning. Nonverbal messages are an essential component of communication in the teaching process. It is not only what you say to your students that is important but also how you say it. An awareness of nonverbal behavior will allow you to become a better receiver of students' messages and a better sender of signals that reinforce learning. Eye contact: Teachers who make eye contact open the flow of communication and convey interest, concern, warmth, and credibility. Facial expressions: Smiling is a great way to communicate friendliness and warmth to students. Gestures: A lively and animated teaching style captures students' attention, makes the material more interesting, and facilitates learning. Head nods also communicate positive reinforcement to students and indicate that you are listening. Posture and body orientation: Standing erect, but not rigid, and leaning slightly forward communicates to students that you are approachable, receptive, and friendly. Speaking with your back turned or looking at the floor or ceiling should be avoided, as it communicates disinterest. Proximity: Cultural norms dictate a comfortable distance for interaction with students. Look for signals of discomfort caused by invading students' space, which includes rocking, leg swinging, crossed arms, tapping, and gaze aversion. Paralinguistics: Tone, pitch, rhythm, timbre, loudness, and inflection in the way you speak should be varied for maximum effectiveness. Students report that they learn less and lose interest more quickly when listening to teachers who have not learned to modulate their voices. Humor: Develop the ability to laugh at yourself and encourage students to do the same. Humor is often overlooked as a teaching tool. It can release stress and tension for both instructor and student and foster a friendly classroom environment that facilitates learning. Motivation is a key factor in student

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanism with the Challenges of Juggling Multiple Roles

success, and whatever level of motivation your student brings to the learning environment will be transformed, for better or worse, by what happens in the learning process. Involve students as active participants in learning. Students learn by doing, making, writing, designing, creating,

and solving. Pose questions. Don't tell students something when you can ask them. Be enthusiastic about what you are teaching. An instructor's enthusiasm is a crucial factor in student motivation. If you become bored or apathetic, students will too.

When possible, let students have some say in choosing what will be studied. Let students decide between two locations for a field trip, or have them select which topics to explore in greater depth. Vary your teaching methods. Variety reawakens students' involvement

in the course and their motivation. Incorporate role-playing, debates, brainstorming, discussion, demonstrations, case studies, audio-visual presentations, guest speakers, or small group work.

3.3. Educational Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study—The study of the experiences of teachers as they explore the challenges of doing dual roles provides several educational insights that can inform future teaching and learning practices. Some of the insights include the importance of work-life balance and the benefits of parental involvement.

faced with a multitude of teaching tasks, one of the areas all teachers can miss, is taking care of themselves.' (Turner and Braine, 2016) Teaching is a privilege! What other job enables you to transform lives? All the hard work put into preparation, planning and assessment are forgotten during those 'lean forward' moments in the classroom when your pupils are so engaged in learning that they physically move towards you, or their peers, to participate more. And once your pupils are engaged, they can develop and flourish, with a whole world of potential opportunities unfolding before them. This said, pupils can only blossom if the ground that is feeding them is well nourished and refreshed. Teaching is a challenging job that can impact negatively on teacher wellbeing (Briner and Drewberry, 2007); (Turner and Braine, 2016).

3.3.1. Importance of Work-Balance Life—Teachers who are also parents face the challenge of balancing their personal and professional responsibilities. This can lead to stress and burnout if not managed effectively. Schools can support these teachers by providing flexible work arrangements and professional development on work-life balance. Teachers need to know how to look after themselves. This may seem a simple and easy task; however, when

Understanding and supporting teacher well-being in schools, and enabling teachers to support themselves, is essential for a sustained healthy learning environment. As teachers, we need to manage these elements. Taking care of our mental and emotional wellbeing can be hard in a busy school, where we experience the demands of others (pupils and other teachers/leaders) and respond to these on a personal level. The physical demands of moving and talking all day can take their toll – as can the social requirement to engage with other teachers, pupils and parents, while remaining professional at all times. These personal demands to wellbeing should not be underestimated for teachers, trainee, NQTs or otherwise. So what can be done to support you as a new teacher in managing your workload as you enter this amazing profession? Here are just a few suggestions that demonstrate ways in which you can help yourself, as well as how you can work with your school leaders, mentor and initial teacher training As a trainee teacher or NQT, you are required to be aware of your professional role and master a number of complex skills quickly, which can be stressful. Those supporting you in school, and in particular your mentor, should hopefully share realistic expectations in relation to your workload. Typically, the ITT provider of a trainee teacher will agree specific task requirements with the school, such as the requirements of lesson planning, and an NQT mentor will set out what is expected of the NQT. The challenge for you comes if these expectations are not clear between those overseeing your training or NQT year. When do you stop working on developing teaching resources, lesson plans, etc.? As trainee teachers and NQTs, it can be hard to recognize when you need to stop working. It is great to have high expectations of yourself in your new role as a teacher, but sometimes this leads to unnecessary pressure and excessive workload. Learning that there are times when ‘good is good enough’ and that work has to stop is important to your

well-being. Savage and Fautley suggest that establishing a balanced approach to work is one of the most important things for a teacher to recognize (Savage and Fautley, 2013). An example of how you might end up working excessively long hours is lesson planning. You may write your lesson plan and then spend hours refining and honing it, concerned that one element may result in your pupils not progressing. You need to remember that if the evidence base suggests that the tasks in your lesson plan will support student progress then that is good enough. Stop there. Bubb and Earley highlighted the negative impact on children, and on learning, when teacher workload becomes impossible to manage (Bubb and Earley, 2004). Seek guidance from your school mentors if you feel that you are spending too long on particular tasks. School systems, processes, and tools can all seem overwhelming when you first encounter them as a trainee or NQT. If you consider that many teachers commit an average of 33 hours a week to non-teaching tasks (Department for Education - a ministerial department response... More, 2016a), it is imperative that you understand how school systems work to enable you to manage your time more effectively. Ideally, you will be supported as a trainee teacher in understanding how to manage your workload and being shown practical and real ways to undertake the essential tasks required by our profession. This support should extend into your NQT year, with your mentor enabling you to discuss your well-being and workload. The Department for Education (DfE) recently produced a report, ‘Reducing Teacher Workload’ (2016a), which not only highlighted concerns across the profession for the long hours that teachers are working but also suggested ways to improve the situation: The DfE is working with schools through a variety of projects, such as those funded by the School Strategic Improvement Fund and the Teaching and Leadership Innovation Funding, to establish an evidence base of best practices

to support changes in working for teachers.

3.3.2. Benefits of Parental Involvement—Teachers who are also parents have the potential to be highly engaged in their children’s education and to bring that experience to the classroom. This can benefit all students by providing a perspective on the parent-teacher relationship and promoting parental involvement in the school community. According to Waterford.org, an organization seeking to help children succeed through access to lifelong education, the participation of parents in the educational process means that teachers and parents share the responsibility to teach students and work together to achieve educational goals. To this end, the organization suggests that teachers invite parents to regular school meetings and events and that parents voluntarily commit to prioritizing these goals. Lamentably, parents’ involvement in the educational process has been in decline since 2016, according to data from Blackboard. Many parents believe that the communication between them and teachers is ineffective, so they prefer online communication (via texts, emails, or social networks) methods rather than to attend conferences or briefings with teachers face-to-face. Although getting more involved would help improve communication, this low attendance reflects declining support and time availability of the parents. According to a meta-analysis of more than fifty studies on parent involvement in high schools, there is a direct connection between students’ academic performance and the participation of parents in their children’s education. Furthermore, the earlier that a connection is established between parents and the educational process of their children, the more robust is the foundation for the success of the student.

3.3.3. Advantages of parental involvement—Parental involvement is essential for student development and offers many benefits. There are many studies, including those mentioned above, that explore how parental participation

can improve students’ success and also teachers’ work. Some of the advantages are: When there is good communication between parents and teachers, absenteeism decreases. According to a report by Johns Hopkins University (JHU), this helps reduce student absenteeism by 24 percent. Academic performance increases. According to JHU, aspects such as comprehension and reading fluency improve when there is parental involvement, even more so if parents spend time reading with their children. The students feel more motivated to learn, and their grades improve. It also helps improve student behavior in the classroom. Having parents and teachers communicate more helps students feel more motivated in their classes; their self-esteem and attitudes in class improve. The benefit extends to all ages. Although the benefits are usually discussed in the context of preschool or elementary school students, there are other studies focused on high school students. Parental involvement is something that makes a difference at all educational levels, although it’s influence decreases as the student progresses in age. Still, in high school, for example, having the parents involved can affect the decision of whether the student wants to continue studying or not. Parental involvement improves teacher performance. When parents have better communication with teachers, they learn to value the work and the challenges that teachers face, which makes the teachers feel appreciated. It also helps the teachers to get to know the student more, allowing them to teach in a more personalized and effective way. It helps when the parents feel happier and more involved with their children’s education. A good connection with the school lets parents understand the curriculum better and the advancement of their children. It also helps them feel more comfortable and happier with the quality of education. It can even motivate those who did not finish their education to continue it.

3.3.4. Disadvantages of parental Involvement—Although parental involvement helps students, it can also have negative connotations. There are several cases where parents become excessively involved, constantly calling the teachers to check their children’s progress, which uses up a lot of the teacher’s time. This can also damage the self-esteem of both the teacher and the student. There is also concern

on the part of the teachers about the extent to which parents should be involved. Teacher recruitment, book selection, and curriculum development, among others, are areas where teachers believe that parents should not be included. To this end, schools should work with parents and teachers to develop policies regarding parental participation and create boundaries so that parents know the limits of their involvement.

3.4. Challenges of parental involvement—One of the biggest challenges is for parents to find the time to attend school events or support their children; this is especially true for families with low economic resources. It is also challenging for the teacher when the children are expected to perform well academically, but the students do not receive any support at home. It is difficult to establish a connection between schools and households or create a safe environment for parents of all socioeconomic statuses. In cases where parents do not know how to read or write, or when their mother tongue is another language than the one that prevails in school, it is difficult for them to feel comfortable attending talks or school events. That is why educational institutions should work even harder to make such parents feel welcome and accepted. Parental involvement is associated with various benefits for students of all ages. There does not even need to be a high level of commitment;

simply by asking the child how he or she did in school and attending school meetings, parents can positively influence the student’s future. According to experts on the subject, the best indicator of a student’s success is the extent to which families are involved in their education. Feeling their parents’ support, students become more motivated and develop a love of learning. From another viewpoint, teachers see important changes in their classrooms when parents get involved, such as improvements in the motivation and performance of the students and even their character. Also, collaboration with parents can help identify needs and goals, and there can be discussions about how parents can contribute. Communication with the parents presents the opportunity for the teacher to listen to parents’ concerns and explain to them more about their children’s education. Thus, parental involvement offers benefits to everyone, including the school, the teachers, the parents, and above all, the students.

4. Implications and Future Directions

Presented in this chapter is a brief overview of the study. It is followed by implications based on the findings of the study. Future directions in the field of school culture are also discussed here. The main objective of this study is to explore the experiences of the teachers doing dual roles for the students. Specifically, it sought to identify the experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of teachers in addressing the challenges of doing dual roles. For their experiences, the teachers have experience in navigating their roles and at the same time maintaining professional boundaries. The participants shared they have to present a fair judgment every time to avoid bias. That the teachers set a schedule for any consultation so that the teachers will have an update with the students. Under the coping mechanism, the participants shared the meaning of fostering a

Fig. 5. Educational Insights Drawn from the Study

positive learning environment for the students. The teachers shared that they encouraged their students to participate in whatever classroom activity.

4.1. Implications—There are several implications that can be drawn from the results of this study. The first theme under the experiences of teachers in doing dual roles is the difficulty in navigating dual roles. Teachers who are also the mothers of their students must juggle their multiple responsibilities as parents and educators. This entails juggling their duties as mothers and teachers while frequently working with the same group of students. Teachers play an important role in the trajectory of students throughout the formal schooling experience. Teachers who support students in the learning environment can positively impact their social and academic outcomes, which is important for the long-term trajectory of school and eventually employment. The next theme, Managing Emotions, has just come to be understood as essential component of teachers’ professional lives. instructors’ feelings are influenced by students’ learning, instructors’ own teaching, and external variables (such as collegial connections, principal support, parental expectations, and educational policies). Teachers rather frequently experience a wide variety of discrete emotions while teaching and interacting with students such as joy, satisfaction, pride, love, anger, exhaustion, hopelessness, anxiety,

shame, or boredom. For the coping mechanisms, themes revealed are the following; first is Establishing boundaries, Setting boundaries is one of the coping strategies instructors use to deal with the difficulties of performing dual tasks. Setting strong boundaries between their personal and professional life might be advantageous for teachers who are also mothers of their pupils. This can entail scheduling certain periods for grading and lesson preparation before giving family time outside of school hours top priority. Second is, Fostering a supportive classroom climate is another coping strategy instructors use to deal with the difficulties of performing dual tasks. Fostering a safe classroom climate where all children feel appreciated and respected can be beneficial for teachers who are also the mothers of their pupils. By doing this, you can lessen any potential conflicts or prejudices brought on by their multiple jobs. The need for flexible work arrangements. Schools should provide teachers who are also parents with flexible work arrangements, such as part-time or job-sharing positions, to help them balance their personal and professional responsibilities. The potential benefits of parental involvement. Schools should recognize and leverage the potential benefits of having teachers who are also parents by

promoting parental involvement in the school community. In summary, the study of the multiple roles of teacher-parents in classroom responsibilities highlights the need for schools to provide support and resources to teachers who are also parents. By doing so, schools can promote a supportive school culture and ensure that all students have access to high-quality instruction.

4.2. *Future Directions*—Studying the experiences of teachers in doing dual roles provide valuable insights into how the teachers can be fair while juggling different roles. Here are some future directions for this type of research. Investigating the impact on student outcomes: While there is some evidence that teachers who are also parents can have a positive impact on student outcomes, further research is needed to explore this relationship in more detail. Future studies could investigate the potential benefits of having teachers who are also parents in the classroom and the conditions under which these benefits are most likely to occur. Investigating

the impact on student outcomes: While there is some evidence that teachers who are also parents can have a positive impact on student outcomes, further research is needed to explore this relationship in more detail. Future studies could investigate the potential benefits of having teachers who are also parents in the classroom and the conditions under which these benefits are most likely to occur. Investigating strategies for supporting teachers who are also parents: Schools can support teachers who are also parents by providing flexible work arrangements, professional development, and a supportive school culture. Future research could explore the effectiveness of these strategies and identify additional approaches for supporting teachers who are also parents. Overall, future research in this area could help to further our understanding of the multiple roles of teachers-parents in classroom responsibilities and identify effective strategies for supporting these teachers and promoting positive outcomes for all students.

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